

**INDUSTRIALIZATION AND COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT
THROUGH TRADITIONAL AGRO-ALLIED VENTURES IN MKPAT
ENIN L.G.A. OF AKWA IBOM STATE**

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Abstract

This study sets to unravel and address some of the numerous problems associated with the age-long traditional agro-allied ventures by employing the concept of industrialization to drive this sector of the economy to a modern standard of development in Mkpato Enin L.G.A. of Akwa Ibom State. The Lewis Model of industrialization and community development theories were made use of in the study. The methodology adopted in this research was the Historical/Descriptive Design. Both primary and secondary data were collected for the study and a single subsidiary objective was set to find out if the locally fabricated machines can be improved upon to drive the local economy to an enviable height in Akwa Ibom State. The research question was geared toward eliciting answers from respondents on whether the locally fabricated machines can be improved upon to drive the local economy to an enviable height in Akwa Ibom State. The research hypothesis was postulated in null (H_0) form to enable empirical verifications in the study. The hypothesis held that the locally fabricated machines may not be improved upon to drive the local economy to an enviable height in Akwa Ibom State. Based on the result, it was recommended that government should improve the standard of the locally fabricated machines to be able to drive the local economy to an enviable height in Akwa Ibom State.

Keywords: Industrialization, Community Development, Traditional, Agro-Allied Ventures.

1. Background to the study

The concept of industrialization has taken various forms depending on where the concept is introduced. In the western world, industrialization has evolved so rapidly to the extent it brings total transformation. But, in the developing societies like Nigeria, etc., the rate of development brought about by industrialization is slow. For instance, in the early 80s and late 90s in Akwa Ibom State, particularly in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area, it was common practice that the local women made use of manual crater, a form of industrial machine to grate or blend cassava and pressed it with four long sticks held together at the base by a rope produced from the inner part of palm frond, weaved together in the form of a ring and tied together on the top-side with two long ropes that were also produced from the inner part of palm frond with each rope holding tight the two sticks together on the cassava paste that was already packed into a white sack bag. The cassava paste would be left in the tight condition over-night for it to drain away the water and starch.

On the following day, the women would lose the bag of cassava paste from the sticks and get it ready for sifting with a local sifter into a big basin. Thereafter, the sifted cassava (this time no more in the paste form but in a wet condition) awaited frying. The next process was the frying. The frying process was done with a kind of open frying pan prepared by the blacksmiths. It was usually very hot when suspended the fire burning with charcoal or firewood.

In my culture and tradition in parts of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, although men were not forbidden to fry garri, the picture usually seems odd whenever a man sat at the fire place to fry garri. People would wonder whether the man had no sisters or wife that should help him fry the garri. As such, garri was most often fried by women in our locality. This process of making small quantity of garri for subsistence purposes usually took at least two days to be completed. By that estimation, one is left to wonder if just the subsistent quantity of garri produced basically for domestic use could take such amount of time, effort and ingenuity, then the cost of producing garri in large quantity for commercial purposes at that time could be unimaginable. Yet, people were still involved in the commercial production of garri at that time, using the same process and with the intention to use the proceeds for payment of school fees for their children.

In a similar process, the palm oil production was another very tasking and prolonged traditional agro-economic engagement before the advent of the locally fabricated machines for oil mill production. In this case, some men who learned how to climb the

palm trees made use of raffia ropes extracted from palm wine trees for that purpose. The robes were specially weaved manually by specialists, and with cutlasses in their hands, the palm fruit tappers climbed the palm trees that yield ripe fruits and tap the fruits. Thereafter, the women and young children (mostly from the kindred of the tapper) would pack the bunches of the palm fruits back home where they were usually kept for about a week or so for it to become softened and easy to prune and separate the seeds from the stalks and chaffs.

Often, the women (and sometimes, men) would separate the palm fruits from the chaffs and kept for processing. As early as 1:00 am or thereabouts (depending on the quantity of the palm fruits), the women will wake up and set their palm fruits on fire. After boiling the fruits for hours (in a large earthen pots) to ensure that by 3.00 am the palm fruits were properly cooked and were ready for pounding, the strong men will come out and do the pounding of the palm fruits with big wooden mortar and long wooden pestles. The mortars were carved out from big logs of wood and the pestles also carved from wood, were sometimes longer than human beings.

Before morning when others are waking up, it was always surprising that the process had gone very far. Most young people never met the pounding stage. But when they finally woke up, they will see their mothers and their assistants sorting and separating the chaffs from the kernels and draining the oil into basins. All the sorting process took place in a large wooden canoe-like calabash. On the final analysis, it is important to note that what come out as the final products are: kernels, chaffs and oil. The oil is squeezed out of the chaffs into various sizes of calabashes or basins. However, the process was usually very tedious, time and energy consuming. The younger people never liked this process, but they had no choice as most of their school fees, feeding money and clothing came from it.

But fortunately today, things have changed drastically and various machines have been fabricated. While some of them are locally made in Nigeria, others are imported from the foreign countries. For instance, a visit to a certain newly constructed Palm Oil Mill in Nya Odiong village in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area where the researchers come from, exposed the researchers to this very Constituency Project which was attracted to Ikot Abasi Federal Constituency by the then House of Representatives member (Rep), Hon. Dr. Akpan Micah Umoh. In his remarks, Dr. Umoh assured the people that the plant saves time, man-power, cost, and energy and also brings about higher productivity, output and efficiency as compared to the erstwhile traditional/manual method of palm oil production of our forebears.

The implication of what the Rep. said was that the functionality of the entire out-fit was that as soon as palm fruits were ferried from the bush, they were thrown into the machine (boiler) in bunches with the chaffs and the stalks without having to separate them. The boiler then boils the fruits at a certain temperature and when it is cooked, the machine pushes the chaffs out into a separator which further separates the chaffs from the palm fruits. The pounder pounds the fruits and moves the whole lumps to another separator that distinctively separates the kernels from the fibers. The fibers get into the oil press and are pressed to extract oil into big containers. And the process continues until the entire large quantity of palm fruits is processed. The process is time and energy saving. It is also very economical and can continue as many times as possible in a day. That is what industrialization has brought to replace the crude methods of existence. This may be the reason Udoh and Mbon (2023) have frowned at western industrialization by seeing it as a “problem of continuous control, subjugation and constant exploitation of the third world countries by the industrialized nations.”

2. Statement of the Problem

There are a number of problems associated with the concepts of industrialization let alone the traditionally agro-cultural system of development in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State where the focus of this study is based. Some of such problems identified in this study include but not limited to lack of electricity; local manpower; crude implements; uncivilized processing methods; traditional and cultural barriers; religion; poor maintenance culture; lack of innovation; lack of dignity in labor; lack of government patronage; poor state of infrastructure including the industrial facilities, bad road network to the market place; high cost of transportation; poor wastes management and environmental hazards, etc.

First and foremost, one of the major reasons why many businesses do not thrive in many societies (be it traditional or modern) is the problem of power. The problem of power, in the context of this study is in relation to lack of electricity. Lack of electricity is the first identified problem in this study. As stated by Udoh (2023), “the problem of electricity in Nigeria, as a whole, dates back to her independence in 1960. Successive governments (both democratic and the military governments) have variously tackled this problem of electricity generation and distribution so much in this country, yet it still seems as though enough efforts have not been put in that direction. No new government has ever emerged in Nigeria without making several promises during campaigns, on how it intends to tackle the problem of electricity in the country”.

One will wonder why and how local manpower can be a problem under this topic. If local manpower will not constitute a problem here in a real sense of the word, at least, the lack of it can. It is unfortunate that many young people do not want to engage in such energy sapping venture. Some others consider local production of garri or palm oil as no longer being in vogue. They see it as an outdated venture, thereby distancing themselves from getting involved in the process. As a result of this, the sector suffers acute manpower shortage, as only a few elderly men and women take to the job.

Aside from the problem of manpower, the industry is bedeviled with poor state of infrastructure including the industrial facilities. The sector still makes use of crude implements. Such implements as high mortars, long and heavy pestles, wide cooking pots, iron pressing machine, and fire, etc. are usually used for the process of producing garri and palm oil in Mkpato Enin L.G.A. of Akwa Ibom State. These make the process very strenuous for the younger generation and they tend to find no dignity in labor in the industry. Uncivilized processing methods are prevalent due to the fact that the implements used in the sector are locally fabricated. Another reason for that is the lack of education and civilization of the operators in the local garri processing and palm oil milling industry.

The major setbacks to this local industry are those things that constitute traditional and cultural barriers. For instance, some communities do not harvest their crops on a particular day of the week, while others have to make sacrifices to their gods or celebrate festivals before their crops are declared ready and safe for harvest. Religion is also a major factor in the local manufacturing industry. Apart from Saturdays and mostly Sundays which are a taboo in this part of the society that work is put on hold because people have to go to the places of worship, there are certain religious beliefs that are inimical to the progress of industry of this nature in the parts of Akwa Ibom State, including Mkpato Enin L.G.A. For instance, it is believed that Sunday is a holy day, therefore, only a pagan can stay away from going to church on Sunday.

Poor maintenance culture on its part has engendered some impediments on the sector. Local individuals do not know what maintenance culture is all about, or how important it is. The few people who have heard about maintenance culture do not take it seriously when it comes to handling the facilities and infrastructure of the local manufacturing industry. Lack of innovation is tied to the level of education and civilization of the operators of the industry. Without proper education or exposure, there can be no innovation in the sector. And, as the case may be, many of those working in these kinds of industries may not have basic education.

For this industry to thrive, there is supposed to be good government patronage. Apart from funding either in terms of provision of loans and grants to the operators of this industry, government is supposed to open a depot where the produce from the local producers are bought over and re-packaged large scale sales and exportation to other parts of the country or continents, respectively. As part of government encouragement, all bad road networks to the market place should be constructed, as this will enhance free movement of products from the industry to the markets. Closely related to bad road network to the market is high cost of transportation. The fuel subsidy removal of the present government of President Asiwaju Bola Amed Tinubu in Nigeria has caused a serious setback to industrial growth and development in the country, including the one under consideration in this study.

On a final note, poor wastes management and environmental hazards have caused all manner of sicknesses and diseases to some of the workers and customers in the sector. The commonest waste management system known to this sector is the digging of an open pit (you may call it a soak away, in modern parlance), which remains open as all the wastes, including cassava/palm fruit chaffs and drained water and condemned oil, etc. are channeled to it. This is a serious impediment to the industry.

3. Objectives of the Study

The **main objective** of this study was to carry out a survey on industrialization and community development through traditional agro-allied ventures in Mkpato Enin L.G.A. of Akwa Ibom State.

Whereas, the only **subsidiary objective** of the study will be:

To find out whether the locally fabricated machines can be improved upon to drive the local economy to an enviable height in Akwa Ibom State.

4. Research Question

In order to elicit answers from respondents, the researcher asked the question below:
Can the locally fabricated industrial machines be improved upon to drive the local economy to an enviable height in Akwa Ibom State?

5. Research Hypothesis

In order to carry out empirical verifications and statistical calculations in this study, a null (H_0) hypothesis was postulated as stated below:

The locally fabricated machines may likely be improved upon to drive the local economy to an enviable height in Akwa Ibom State.

6. Methodology of the Study

The methodology adopted in this research was the Historical/Descriptive Survey design. Methods of enquiry included the primary and secondary methods of data collection. The primary method involved personal observation and interviews of people considered to be aware of and conversant with the problem at hand as well as the use of questionnaire forms. On the other hand, the secondary data were collected from text books, journals, conference papers, government's official publication, newspapers, magazines and the internet.

7. Significance of the study:

The significance of the study was segmented into two perspectives, namely theoretical and empirical significance.

i. Theoretical significance:

The research will contribute immensely to the existing body of knowledge, and as such, it will serve as reference material for future researchers in the field of industrialization generally, and community development, in particular.

ii. Empirical significance:

The knowledge acquired from the study on industrialization and community development will help to proffer lasting solution to the challenges surrounding the concept in Mkpato Enin L.G.A. in Akwa Ibom State. It is hoped that the study will help the government, particularly the law makers to make suitable legislations that will encourage the continued collaboration between the two concepts - industrialization and community development.

The experts will find this material useful in carrying out their official assignments both in the public and private concerns. The executive also will realize the importance of preserving government equity share in the partnership business, and as such, will put in place measures that will enhance the smooth operation and collaboration of industrialization and community development.

8. Definition of terms

I. **Industrialization:** The process in which a society or country (or world) transforms itself from a primarily agricultural society into one based on the manufacturing of goods and services. **Industrialisation** (in British English) or **industrialization** (in American English) is the period of social and economic change that transforms a human group from an agrarian society into an industrial one. It is a part of a wider modernization process, where social change and economic

development are closely related with technological innovation, particularly with the development of large-scale energy and metallurgy production.

ii. **Traditional:** A **tradition** is a belief or behavior (**folk custom**) passed down within a group or society with a symbolic meaning or special significance with origins in the past. Traditions can persist and evolve for thousands of years—the word *tradition* itself is derived from the Latin *trader* literally meaning to transmit, to hand over, to give for safekeeping. While it is commonly assumed that traditions have an ancient history, many traditions have been invented on purpose, whether that be political or cultural over short periods of time. Various academic disciplines also use the word in a variety of ways.

iii. **Community Development:** Community Development can be defined as a process where community members come together to take collective action and generate solutions to common problems.

iv. **Mkpat-Enin L.G.A.:**

Mkpat-Enin is located in the South South region of Nigeria and is a town and a Local Government Area (LGA) in Akwa Ibom State. It sits at an altitude of approximately 185 metres (607 ft) above sea level. Mkpat Enin LGA has an area of 322.352 square kilometres (124.461 sq mi) and it is the second largest local government area in Akwa Ibom State. The LGA is located within the industrial belt extending from Eastern Obolo, Etinan, Oruk Anam, Onna, to Ikot Abasi. The people are traditionally Ibibio speakers. The population was 178,036 based on the 2006 census. The area is rich in oil and natural gas; oil was discovered in Ikot Akpa/Ekop as early as 1953. Forest reserves in the local government area include timber and palm produce. One of the campuses of the Akwa Ibom State University of Technology is located in this community. The LGA has four clans and 87 villages. The Present Executive Chairman of Mkpat Enin LGA 9 (as at the time of this research) is Hon. (Prince) Anieokpon E. Ekpo.

Economy: Mkpat Enin LGA is wealthy in stores of raw petroleum and flammable gas and the exercises of neighborhood and worldwide oil mining firms in the LGA contributes monstrously to the financial advancement of the area. Fishing is likewise a basic part of the economy of Mkpat Enin LGA with the area's waterways and streams being wealthy in fish. Cultivating likewise prospers in Mkpat Enin LGA with harvests, for example, plantain and vegetables filled nearby.

v. **Agro Allied Ventures**

An agro-allied venture is an agro-based business. Agro-allied ventures involve various chains of agriculture like farming, processing, sales and supplying. This has to do with farms that handle crops, poultry and general animal production. In today's world, Agriculture is the anchor of food production in all parts of the world. In the context of this research, agro-allied ventures involve garri and palm oil processing in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area.

Review of Related Literature and Theoretical Framework
The Concept of Industrialization

Udoh (2014) opines that industrialization (or industrialisation) is a process that happens in countries when they start to use machines to do work that was once done by people. Industrialization changes the society as it happens. During the industrialization of a country, people leave farming work to take higher paid jobs in factories in towns. Industrialization is part of a process where people adopt easier and cheaper ways to make things. Using better technology, it becomes possible to produce more goods in a shorter amount of time.

After industrialization, people also do more specialized jobs. For example before industrialization, a cobbler who had to make a whole shoe would work on one pair of shoes, and must finish that before making another. With industrialization, there are many people involved in making shoes. An individual shoemaker has a smaller task, however. There is one person that cuts the sole of the shoe. Another person stitches it on. In short, there is division of labor. The machines to make the shoes with cost a lot of money so the factory will be owned by a rich person who can afford the machines. Industrialization started in England with the industrial revolution in the 18th century. It spread first to parts of Europe, and to North America. In the 20th century, industrialization spread to most other countries.

This concept is a process in which a society or country (or world) transforms itself from a primarily agricultural society into one based on the manufacturing of goods and services. Individual manual labor is often replaced by mechanized mass production, and craftsmen are replaced by assembly lines. Characteristics of industrialization include the use of technological innovation to solve problems as opposed to superstition or dependency upon conditions outside human control such as the weather, as well as more efficient division of labor and economic growth.

Industrialisation (in British English) or **industrialization** (in American English) is the period of social and economic change that transforms a human group from an agrarian society into an industrial one. It is a part of a wider modernization process, where social change and economic development are closely related with technological innovation, particularly with the development of large-scale energy and metallurgy production. Industrialization also introduces a form of philosophical

change where people obtain a different attitude towards their perception of nature, and a sociological process of ubiquitous rationalization.

There is considerable literature on the factors facilitating industrial modernization and enterprise development. Key positive factors identified by researchers have ranged from favourable politico-legal environments for industry and commerce through abundant natural resources of various kinds, to plentiful supplies of relatively low-cost, skilled and adaptable labor. As industrial workers' incomes rise, markets for consumer goods and services of all kinds tend to expand and provide a further stimulus to industrial investment and economic growth. The first country to industrialize was the United Kingdom during the Industrial Revolution, commencing in the 18th century. By the end of the 20th century, East Asia had become one of the most recently industrialized regions of the world.

Historical Perspective of Industrialization

Most pre-industrial economies had standards of living not much above subsistence. Among that, the majority of the population was focused on producing for their means of survival. For example, in medieval Europe, as much as 80% of the labor force was employed in subsistence agriculture. Some pre-industrial economies such as classical Athens, had trade and commerce as significant factors so native Greeks could enjoy wealth far beyond a sustenance standard of living through the use of slavery.

Famines were frequent in most pre-industrial societies, although some, such as the Netherlands and England of the 17th and 18th centuries, the Italian city states of the 15th century, the medieval Islamic Caliphate, and the ancient Greek and Roman civilizations were able to escape the famine cycle through increasing trade and commercialization of the agricultural sector. It is estimated that during the 17th century, Netherlands imported nearly 70% of its grain supply and in the 5th century BC, Athens imported three-quarters of its total food supply. Industrialization through innovation in manufacturing processes first started with the Industrial Revolution in the north-west and Midlands of England in the 18th century. It spread to Europe and North America in the 19th century.

Industrialization in the Developing Countries

It would be noted that despite the goodness of industrialization which includes time saving, maximization of profit, large scale production of goods and services, innovation, specialization, division of labor, etc., industrialization down-sizes the labor strength in any organization or society (Udoh, 2014).

Take for instance, in a trip for a survey in a local shoe-making factory that had four staff to handle shoe mending daily, now purchased both mending and shoe filing machines. It was found that the time that each of the four staff spent in mending one shoe could be used by the business owner alone to produce four shoes a day with the help of the machines without anybody lending a helping hand. This development

made the proprietor of the shoe mending factory to sack the three others and save money from their monthly stipends, while only one staff was retained to operate the two machines at the same salary rate. He rather advertised for trainees to apply in the shoe making company. The trainees were not on monthly salaries from the company, yet while on training increased the productivity level of the company free of charge. Incidentally, industrialization takes the place of labor force and renders people jobless. This joblessness also renders an average Nigerian household or family hungry and famished.

Also, taking into consideration the just concluded Joint Admission and Matriculation Board (JAMB) examination, everything about JAMB (before now) was done manually by humans. But in recent times, the introduction of computer-based examination (e-examination) renders a whole spectrum of Nigerians who used to serve as supervisors, centre coordinators, examiners, etc. jobless. This is because electronic devices have taken over these manual duties that used to create employment opportunities for Nigerians. Many employees have lost their jobs due to the introduction of technology like computers, laptops, telephones, internet, etc. Lately, letter writing is no longer in vogue. Mails and parcels are rarely being conveyed lately to the owners by mail boys who were employees of post offices or courier companies. Most of the works that were done by mail boys and expert riders are now taken over by the internet.

Community Development

The United Nations defines **community development** as "a process where community members come together to take collective action and generate solutions to common problems." It is a broad concept applied to the practices of civic leaders, activists, involved citizens, and professionals to improve various aspects of communities, typically aiming to build stronger and more resilient local communities.

Community development is also understood as a professional discipline, and is defined by the International Association for Community Development as "a practice-based profession and an academic discipline that promotes participative democracy, sustainable development, rights, economic opportunity, equality and social justice, through the organization, education and empowerment of people within their communities, whether these be of locality, identity or interest, in urban and rural settings".

Community development seeks to empower individuals and groups of people with the skills they need to effect change within their communities. These skills are often created through the formation of social groups working for a common agenda. Community developers must understand both how to work with individuals and how to affect communities' positions within the context of larger social institutions. *Community development* as a term has taken off widely in anglophone countries, i.e. the United States, United Kingdom, Australia, Canada, New Zealand, as well as other

countries in the Commonwealth of Nations. It is also used in some countries in Eastern Europe with active community development associations in Hungary and Romania. The *Community Development Journal*, published by Oxford University Press, since 1966, has aimed to be the major forum for research and dissemination of international community development theory and practice.

Community development approaches are recognized internationally. These methods and approaches have been acknowledged as significant for local social, economic, cultural, environmental and political development by such organizations as the UN, WHO, OECD, World Bank, Council of Europe and EU. There are a number of institutions of higher education such as the University of Toronto, Leiden University, SOAS University of London, and the Balsillie School of International Affairs, among others offering community development as an area of study and research.

Furthermore, the United Nations defines *community development* broadly as "a process where community members come together to take collective action and generate solutions to common problems." The International Association for Community Development (IACD) defines it as both a practice based profession and an academic discipline. Following the adoption of the IACD definition in 2016, the association has gone on to produce International Standards for Community Development Practice. The values and ethos that should underpin practice can be expressed as: Commitment to rights, solidarity, democracy, equality, environmental and social justice. The purpose of community development is understood by IACD as being to work with communities to achieve participative democracy, sustainable development, rights, economic opportunity, equality and social justice.

This practice is carried out by people in different roles and contexts, including people explicitly called professional community workers (and people taking on essentially the same role but with a different job title), together with professionals in other occupations ranging from social work, adult education, youth work, health disciplines, environmental education, local economic development, to urban planning, regeneration, architecture and more who seek to apply community development values and adopt community development methods. Community development practice also encompasses a range of occupational settings and levels from development roles working with communities through to managerial and strategic community planning roles.

The Community Development Challenge report, which was produced by a working party comprising leading UK organizations in the field and including the (now defunct) Community Development Foundation, the (now defunct) Community Development Exchange and the (now defunct) Federation for Community Development Learning, defines community development as;

A set of values and practices which plays a special role in overcoming poverty and disadvantage, knitting society together at the grass roots and deepening democracy.

There is a community development profession, defined by national occupational standards and a body of theory and experience going back the best part of a century. There are active citizens who use community development techniques on a voluntary basis, and there are also other professions and agencies which use a community development approach or some aspects of it.

Community Development Exchange defines community development as both an occupation (such as a community development worker in a local authority) and a way of working with communities. Its key purpose is to build communities based on justice, equality and mutual respect. Community development involves changing the relationships between ordinary people and people in positions of power so that everyone can take part in the issues that affect their lives. It starts from the principle that within any community there is a wealth of knowledge and experience which, if used in creative ways, can be channeled into collective action to achieve the communities' desired goals.

Community development practitioners work alongside people in communities to help build relationships with key people and organizations and to identify common concerns. They create opportunities for the community to learn new skills, enabling people to act together, and help to foster social inclusion and equality.

7. Theoretical Framework

Two theories adopted in this study were both the theory of Structural Change and the community development theory (Empowerment Theory).

i. Structural Change Theory - The Lewis Model

The Lewis model presented in 1955, dominated development theory between the 1960s and 1970s. It is also known as the two sector model, and the surplus labor model. It focused on the need for countries to transform their structures away from agriculture with low productivity of labor, towards industrial activity with a high productivity of labor.

ii. Community Development Theory

Community Development Theory is the most practical framework for social workers seeking lasting change for individuals and the communities and societies in which they live. It focuses on the centrality of oppressed people in the process of overcoming externally imposed social problems (Allison Tan, 2009). This theory is community development work because by the mere fact of the definition, it speaks for itself. The theory could adapt to other disciplines like Neighborhood Development.

Empowerment Theory

Empowerment Theory refers to the experience of personal growth and an improvement in self-definition that occurs as a result of the development of capabilities and proficiencies (Staples, 1990). Another definition suggests that empowerment is a combination of personal strengths, initiative, and natural helping systems to bring about change (Perkins & Zimmerman, 1995). This theory can be applied to community development by empowering the people within the community to develop their own community. The theory can adapt to other disciplines like Sociology.

8. Discussion on findings and Application of the Theories in this study

The Lewis model focused on the need for countries to transform their structures away from agriculture with low productivity of labor, towards industrial activity with a high productivity of labor.

In the Lewis model, the line of argument runs thus:

- i. An economy starts with two sectors - a rural agricultural sector and an urban industrial sector. Agriculture generally under-employs workers and the marginal productivity of agricultural labor is virtually zero.
- ii. Therefore, transferring workers out of agriculture does not reduce productivity in the whole economy.
- iii. Labor is then released for work in the more productive, urban, industrial sector.
- iv. Industrialization is now possible given the increase in the supply of workers who have moved from the land.
- v. Industrial firms start to make profits, which can be re-invested into even more industrialization, and capital starts to accumulate.
- vi. As soon as capital accumulates, further economic development can sustain itself.

Community development theory on the other hand, is said to be the most practical framework for social workers seeking lasting change for individuals and the communities and societies in which they live. This has enabled various communities in Mkpato Enin L.G.A. to evolve over a period of time, from purely agrarian communities to semi-civilized societies. Some of such communities include, but are not limited to Minya, Ikot Obiokoi and Ikot Abasi Ufon in Ukpum Minya clan; Ikot Ebak, Ikot Aka Nung Ntok and Nya Odiong in Ibiaku clan; Iffe Town, Ikot Umiang and Ikot Eyienge in Ikpa Ikono clan; and Ikot Ekong, Ikot Akpan Ukam and Atanuk in Ikpa Ibom clan.

According to Allison Tan (2009), the theory focuses on the centrality of oppressed people in the process of overcoming externally imposed social problems. Looking at the people of Mkpato Enin L.G.A., one will agree with this study that the people have come a long way from a remote setting to what it is at present. A lot of oppressions would have been fought against to arrive at the present level of development.

Specifically, the Empowerment Theory which refers to the experience of personal growth and an improvement in self-definition that occurs as a result of the development of capabilities and proficiencies as opined by Staples (1990), gives credence on how various individuals and communities, as mentioned above, have engaged in personal growth and improvement of their environments through the use of the traditional agro-allied ventures. In Perkins & Zimmerman (1995) definition, the scholar suggests that empowerment is a combination of personal strengths, initiative, and natural helping systems to bring about change.

Going by that definition, some communities in Mkpato Enin L.G.A. have engaged a combination of their personal strengths, initiative, and natural helping systems to bring about change in the entire local government area, vis-à-vis, Akwa Ibom State. This theory is applied purely to community development by empowering the people within the community to develop their own community. By reason of this empowerment, many people as well as communities have benefited immensely from the traditional agro-allied ventures and are conspicuously standing out today in the local government area.

9. Recommendation

Based on the fact that this study was purely historical and narrative due to its longitudinal nature, a single recommendation was made in this study as stated below:

The government should encourage the improvement of locally fabricated machines in order to drive the local economy to an enviable height in Akwa Ibom State.

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